

Research Data Management + Primary Materials Toolkit

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

Queensland University of Technology, Charles Darwin University

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

The project was focused on upgrading research data management planning activities which include metadata standardisation and DOI minting for datasets. Charles Darwin University (CDU) has completed the metadata standardisation process and we have put a process in place to mint DOIs for all the datasets.

In Phase 2, the project was mainly focused on evaluating and implementing the Queensland University of Technology (QUT) research data management planning and primary material Checklist (RDM+PM Checklist) at CDU.

CDU is collaborating with QUT and completed the evaluation process of the QUT RDM+PM toolkit.

CDU and QUT have an agreement and are working on the feasibility of implementing the toolkit in CDU as a proof of concept and to leverage on each other's resources.

The overall aim of Phase 2 of this project is to assess the feasibility of piloting deployment of the CDU RDM+PM toolkit based on CDU input and follow-up discussions on future phases of this project to evolve this Institutional Underpinnings into 'cross-institutional' activity that will share/exchange best practice and implement viable solutions at partner institutions.

Project Activities:

1. Enhance and standardise metadata for all CDU dataset – Completed
2. Mint DOI for all CDU dataset – Completed
3. Enhance and update the Data Management Plan template based on outcomes of Phase 1 – After the feasibility of QUT RDM+PM Checklist, CDU has decided to build a CDU RDM+PM Checklist and implement it in CDU - Completed
4. Currently, CDU is undertaking stakeholder engagement within CDU about the fields in the toolkit
5. Streamline data management planning using technology to make the process easier for researchers – Tested the integration with CDU PURE system and it was successful
6. Work with QUT to evaluate the feasibility of deploying the QUT RDM+PM Checklist and implement it in CDU as a proof of concept – Completed
7. QUT/CDU signed confidentiality agreement for QUT to access CDU systems – Completed
8. Working with QUT to implement the QUT RDM+PM Checklist in CDU with CDU branding and system integrations – aim to deliver by end 2022
9. Learning from the QUT experience. QUT has run a number of online demonstration/information sessions to USQ, CDU and University of Canberra – an ongoing process

10. Enhance support, training, and guidance around Research Data Management Planning

11. Await feedback from ARDC on API Keys for use of ARDC RAiD

Resulting Improvements

The RDM+PM Checklist will result in a significant improvement to data management planning at the CDU. This project will improve our data management planning, make the experience easier for researchers and lead to improvements in other elements of the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#).

This project will also improve collaboration with universities such as QUT, UC and University of Southern Queensland on an ongoing basis for future work.

Next Steps

CDU will finalise an agreement with QUT for further work to maintain the toolkit and continue the progress for future development. This arrangement will be reviewed at a future date to discuss continuing or hosting at CDU. CDU and QUT will discuss further allocation and leveraging each other's resources. CDU and QUT are looking at future work to enhance the toolkit for specific types of data including sensitive data, clinical trials, etc.

Project Outputs

Project outputs include:

1. Research data metadata standardisation
2. DOI minting process for datasets for better discovery and access
3. As feasibility testing is done, other universities can evaluate and implement it as well
4. Sharing the CDU experience working with QUT
5. Training materials, guidance, and documentation
6. Feedback on engagement with ARDC RAiD team

Contact eresearch@qut.edu.au for information or to learn more about other implementation phases.

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).